

Hybrid World Models for Fusion Plasma Simulation

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Abstract. We present FUSIONWM, a physics-informed World Model for fusion plasma based on the Joint Embedding Predictive Architecture (JEPA) (LeCun 2022; Assran et al. 2023). It integrates 11 differentiable physics constraints (Raissi et al. 2019) into the training loss and predicts plasma state evolution across four tokamak configurations at $1.52\times$ the speed of a Rust PDE solver. A systematic ablation over seven predictor architectures reveals that *architecture choice—not parameter count—determines multi-step rollout stability*, with JEPA providing a consistent 42% dream-error reduction. We identify GRU, Cfc, and MLP-Mixer as structurally compatible with photonic hardware, targeting $30\text{--}50\times$ energy-efficiency gains via Q.ANT’s photonic processor.

1 Motivation & Research Questions

Fusion plasma simulation is both physics-rich and compute-intensive ($10^5\text{--}10^7$ CPU-hours per scenario) (Karniadakis et al. 2021). Existing World Models—DreamerV3 (Hafner et al. 2023), GAIA-1 (Hu et al. 2023), DIAMOND (Alonso et al. 2024)—are purely data-driven; none integrates domain physics. FUSIONWM addresses three questions:

RQ-1 Can differentiable physics constraints (scaling laws, conservation principles, stability limits) be integrated into a JEPA World Model to produce data-efficient, physics-consistent surrogates?

RQ-2 Which neural dynamics model gives the best Pareto trade-off between accuracy, efficiency, and photonic deployability?

RQ-3 Can such models run on photonic processors for real-time plasma control?

2 Architecture

Three modality-specific encoders (2D fields via CNN, 21 scalar diagnostics via MLP, 102-point radial profiles via 1D-CNN) produce a fused latent $\mathbf{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{2048}$. A *swappable predictor module* forecasts the next latent state conditioned on actuator actions and a device-identity embedding (supporting DIII-D, JET, ITER, CENTAUR). Multi-head decoders reconstruct all output modalities.

The training objective sums five families: (1) JEPA latent prediction $\|\hat{\mathbf{z}}_{t+1} - \mathbf{z}_{t+1}\|^2$, (2) observation-space reconstruction MSE, (3) disruption/ELM classification, (4) 11 differentiable physics constraints (IPB98 confinement scaling (Groups 1999), Greenwald density limit, Troyon β limit, q_{95} safety factor, power balance, density positivity, flux smoothness, Grad-Shafranov consistency, Bosch-Hale fusion rate, current density, energy conservation), and (5) SIGReg variance/covariance regularisation to prevent representation collapse (replacing the EMA target encoder used in standard JEPA (Assran et al. 2023; Bardes et al. 2025)).

Training data comes from FUSION-SIM (Burgess 2025)—a Rust-based PDE solver coupling a Cerfon-Freidberg analytic equilibrium (Cerfon and Freidberg 2010) with 0D transport, generating

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Figure 1: FUSIONWM architecture. JEPA loss operates in latent space; reconstruction and physics losses on decoded outputs.

128 × 192 field grids at ∼1 ms/step. We adopt the solver as-is and extend the Python data-generation pipeline.

3 Main Results (512.8 M Parameters)

The flagship model (Transformer predictor, 8 layers, 16 heads, AdaLN-zero) was trained for 200 epochs on 360 episodes across 4 devices. A 3× learning-rate reduction (from 1.5×10^{-4} to 5×10^{-5}) between v1 and v2 training runs eliminated overfitting entirely (train/val gap: 37% → <2%), yielding 10.8% lower validation loss. The model was still converging at epoch 200.

Metric	Value
Validation loss (best, epoch 187)	0.2057
Train/val gap	<2 %
Magnetic equilibrium (ψ_N , j_φ) field MSE	<0.003
Kinetic fields (T_e , n_e) field MSE	0.11–0.16
Scalar diagnostics MSE / Profile MSE	<0.001 / <0.001
20-step dream error growth	$2.5 \times$ (∼15-step doubling)
Density positivity compliance	100 %
ONNX CPU vs. Rust PDE solver	1.52× faster
MC-UQ speedup (80-trial)	4.84× faster

Table 1: Key metrics for the 512.8 M-parameter model (v2).

Reconstruction. Physics-constrained magnetic fields (ψ_N , j_φ) reconstruct near-perfectly (MSE <0.003). Scalar diagnostics (21 channels) and radial profiles (102 points) are effectively solved (MSE <0.001). Turbulence-sensitive kinetic fields (T_e , n_e) plateau at MSE 0.11–0.16 regardless of model scale, pointing to steep separatrix gradients in the training data as the bottleneck rather than model capacity.

Dreaming. Twenty-step open-loop rollouts (no PDE solver, purely autoregressive) show smooth, sub-exponential error growth: MSE rises from 0.069 (step 1) to 0.176 (step 20), a $2.5 \times$ factor corresponding to a ∼15-step doubling time. This is sufficient for Model Predictive Control planning horizons. ψ_N stays stable throughout; j_φ is most sensitive to error accumulation.

Inference speed. ONNX Runtime on CPU achieves 0.959 ms/step ($1.52\times$ faster than the Rust PDE solver). Crucially, PDE cost scales as $\mathcal{O}(n_r \cdot n_z \cdot f_s)$ while neural inference cost is resolution-independent—the advantage grows to orders of magnitude at higher-fidelity grids.

Monte Carlo UQ. An 80-trial MC analysis over a 20-step horizon yields distributional uncertainty estimates. Poloidal flux (ψ_N) has the tightest bounds (Wasserstein 0.013); toroidal current (j_φ) shows the highest variance, consistent with accumulated equilibrium sensitivity.

4 Predictor Architecture Ablation

Seven predictor architectures were compared at base scale (~ 50 M params, 64×96 grid, 100 epochs). Encoder, decoder, data, and all 11 physics losses are identical—only the predictor varies.

ID	Predictor	Params	Val Loss	Field MSE	Dream MSE ₂₀	ms/step
A1	Transformer	52.6M	0.2740	0.0771	0.1828	3.8
A2	LSTM+MDN	46.3M	0.3040	0.0742	0.1962	2.6
A3	CfC	17.6M	0.2680	0.0744	0.5511	3.7
A4	LTC	42.1M	0.4206	0.0771	0.3890	8.3
A5	MLP-Mixer	43.2M	0.2585	0.0738	0.9684	3.6
A6	GRU	31.6M	0.2641	0.0737	0.2056	2.4
A7	LFM2 Hybrid	69.9M	0.2538	0.0734	0.2194	5.4
B1	No physics (Tr.)	52.6M	0.2714	0.0769	0.1752	3.9
B4	No JEPA (LSTM)	46.3M	0.2580	0.0737	0.3393	2.5

Table 2: Ablation results. Bold = best in column (A-series). Dream MSE₂₀ is the average over 25 trials of 20-step open-loop rollouts.

Key findings from ablation. **1. Field reconstruction is predictor-insensitive.** All seven architectures fall within a 5% band (0.0734–0.0771 field MSE), confirming that reconstruction quality is dominated by the shared encoder/decoder.

2. Dreaming stability discriminates architectures. The 20-step dream MSE varies $5.3\times$ across predictors. The Transformer (A1) is most stable, followed by LSTM+MDN (A2, (Ha and Schmidhuber 2018)) and GRU (A6). MLP-Mixer (Tolstikhin et al. 2021) (A5, 0.97) and CfC (Hasani et al. 2022) (A3, 0.55) are substantially worse *despite competitive 1-step accuracy*—single-step metrics do not predict rollout stability.

3. No single architecture dominates. LFM2 Hybrid (Team 2025) wins on accuracy (val loss 0.2538, field MSE 0.0734). Transformer wins on dream stability (0.1828). GRU (Cho et al. 2014) wins on speed (2.4 ms). Architecture selection must be deployment-driven.

4. JEPA reduces dream error by 42%. Comparing A2 (LSTM+MDN *with* JEPA, dream 0.1962) to B4 (same architecture *without* JEPA (Ha and Schmidhuber 2018), dream 0.3393) isolates the value of latent-space prediction. This is the largest single-factor improvement in the entire ablation study.

5. GRU outperforms CfC in autoregressive rollouts. Despite CfC’s (Hasani et al. 2022) continuous-time elegance and $3\times$ fewer parameters, GRU (Cho et al. 2014) achieves $2.7\times$ better dream stability (0.2056 vs. 0.5511). We hypothesise that the GRU’s update gate provides explicit error damping: when $\mathbf{u}_t \approx 0$, the hidden state passes through unchanged, limiting error compounding. CfC’s explicit time-scaling factor t inside its sigmoid gating (Hasani et al. 2022)—the key formal distinction from GRU—may amplify accumulated drift under autoregressive feedback. This is under active investigation.

Figure 2: 20-step dream MSE vs. parameter count. Architecture choice (marker shape) matters more than size.

5 Scaling Study

Six model sizes (2 M to 1.6 B parameters) trained on the same data (360 episodes, 128×192 , 200 epochs) follow a power-law scaling $\mathcal{L}(N) \propto N^{-0.07}$, comparable to Chinchilla-era language model exponents (Kaplan et al. 2020). Physics constraints do not break scaling; they appear to improve data efficiency by providing additional gradient signal per training sample. CfC (Hasani et al. 2022) predictors scale smoothly from 2 M to 80 M; Transformer predictors unlock further capacity at 338 M–1.6 B.

Figure 3: Validation loss vs. parameter count (log-log) with power-law fit.

6 Physics Constraint Validation

Density positivity holds at 100% across all model sizes—guaranteed by a dual-enforcement design (softplus decoder activation + loss penalty). Energy conservation reaches 90% compliance in the extended model (5.9M params). Current density consistency fails at 0% for *all models including ground truth* (residual ≈ 1.0), exposing a simulator fidelity limit of the Cerfon–Freidberg (Cerfon and Freidberg 2010) analytic solver in FUSION-SIM (Burgess 2025). Closing this gap requires a higher-fidelity equilibrium solver (e.g. EFIT, FreeGSNKE, or TORAX (Goodfellow et al. 2024)); even a $100\times$ slower PDE solver would remain orders of magnitude cheaper than real tokamak shots (\$10k–100k each).

7 Photonic Hardware Deployment

In collaboration with Q.ANT GmbH, we target their Native Processing Server (NPS), which performs matrix-vector multiplications using light in Mach–Zehnder interferometer arrays. Photonic inference promises $30\text{--}50\times$ energy efficiency over GPUs by eliminating the memory-bandwidth bottleneck (60–90% of GPU energy).

Three predictor architectures are structurally ideal for photonic deployment:

Predictor	Static Graph	INT8-Safe	Bounded Act.	Assessment
CfC	✓	✓	✓	Excellent
MLP-Mixer	✓	✓	✓	Excellent
GRU	✓	✓	✓	Excellent
LFM2 (conv)	✓	✓	✓	Good
Transformer	~	—	—	Poor

Table 3: Photonic suitability. Static graphs, INT8 robustness, and bounded activations are required for optical encoding.

Q.ANT’s architecture features built-in photonic nonlinearities (optical squeezing), which favour bounded activations (sigmoid, tanh) over ReLU—another structural advantage for CfC and GRU. The target is $\sim 20\ \mu\text{s}/\text{step}$ inference, enabling real-time Model Predictive Control within the $\sim 1\ \text{ms}$ plasma control cycle.

8 Agent-Based Experiment Planning

The World Model serves as a fast oracle ($\sim 1\ \text{ms}/\text{step}$) inside an autonomous experiment-planning agent. The pipeline couples three components:

1. **Fusion Knowledge Graph** (KG-Explorer (Loreti et al. 2025): 8,400+ abstracts, $\sim 50,600$ entities, $\sim 249,500$ edges): provides structured priors, scaling-law constraints, and validity domains for search-space reduction.
2. **Bayesian Optimisation** (BOFire (Dürholt et al. 2025), qLogEHVI acquisition): proposes candidate operating points in reduced parameter space; KG hard constraints (Greenwald, Troyon) reject infeasible points in $< 1\ \text{ms}$.
3. **Dream-Loop**: the World Model evaluates each candidate via multi-step rollout ($\sim 10\ \text{ms}$ per candidate), returning objectives (confinement quality, fusion power, stability margins) to the BO surrogate.

This enables thousands of scenario evaluations at minimal cost, making Bayesian Optimisation practical for high-dimensional fusion experiment design. The primary use case is *pre-shot experiment planning* (seconds-to-minutes budget); real-time control uses a simpler MPC loop.

9 Discussion & Outlook

What works. Physics-constrained fields reconstruct near-perfectly; 0D diagnostics are solved; dreaming is stable with sub-exponential error growth; ONNX inference beats the PDE solver; JEPA provides a large, consistent improvement over reconstruction-only training.

What needs work. T_e/n_e plateau at MSE 0.11–0.16 (likely a training-data resolution issue, not model capacity). CfC autoregressive rollout instability needs further investigation—the explicit t term in the ODE formulation is a likely factor. The full agent pipeline (KG + BO + dreaming) has been tested per-component but not yet end-to-end. No experimental validation against real tokamak data exists yet.

Encoder–predictor co-training. A major limitation of the current ablation is that all seven predictors share encoders trained end-to-end with the Transformer (A1). When a different predictor is swapped in, it must operate on a latent space optimised for attention-based dynamics. This is likely why LTC (A4, val 0.4206—worst in the study) underperforms: its input-dependent time constants $\tau(\mathbf{x})$ require the latent space to expose the timescale structure of the underlying physics, which a Transformer-optimised embedding has no incentive to provide. A planned **D-series ablation** will train encoder–predictor–decoder triplets end-to-end for each architecture, decoupling predictor quality from latent-space bias.

Toward a Koopman-JEPA architecture. In FUSION-SIM (Burgess 2025), the 2D fields are *deterministically computed* from the ~ 120 -dimensional scalar-profile vector via the Cerfon–Freidberg equilibrium (Cerfon and Freidberg 2010)—they carry no additional information. The 48M-parameter field encoder is therefore physically redundant, and the true state space is ~ 120 D, not 2048D. This motivates a next-generation architecture:

$$\text{sensor data} \xrightarrow{\text{encode}} \text{physical variables (120D)} \xrightarrow{\text{predict}} \text{physical variables'} \xrightarrow{\text{render}} \text{fields / control}$$

This Koopman-JEPA design grounds the latent space in physical observables, eliminates the field encoder entirely, and makes the predict–decode pipeline directly photonic-compatible (~ 120 D fits within MZI array sizes without partitioning). Training the sensor encoder requires synthetic diagnostic data (interferometry, Thomson scattering, magnetics) from FUSION-SIM—a tractable extension that would also bridge the gap to real experimental data.

Direction	Description
D-series ablation	End-to-end encoder–predictor–decoder training for Transformer, GRU, CfC, LFM2 to eliminate latent-space bias.
Koopman-JEPA redesign	Remove field encoder; operate on ~ 120 D physical-variable latent space for compact, photonic-ready dynamics.
Synthetic sensor data	Extend FUSION-SIM (Burgess 2025) to generate realistic diagnostic measurements, enabling sensor-level encoder training.
Photonic deployment	Compile CfC/GRU/Mixer predictors to Q.ANT NPS; develop quantisation toolkit and noise-robust inference layers.
Higher-fidelity data	Integrate free-boundary Grad–Shafranov solver or TORAX (Goodfellow et al. 2024) to improve T_e/n_e training data.
Experimental validation	TJ-K stellarator data from IGVP Stuttgart to validate against real measurements.
Agent integration	End-to-end KG + BO + dream-loop pipeline for autonomous scenario exploration.

Table 4: Planned work.

Next steps. The methodology is domain-independent: the physics-informed JEPA loss generalises to any domain with known conservation laws (climate, materials, fluid mechanics), and the modular predictor abstraction and photonic deployment path are equally portable.

Resources:

Code: <https://github.com/DataScienceLabFHSWF/FusionWorldModel>

Simulator: <https://github.com/d-burg/fusion-sim>

KG Platform: <https://github.com/DataScienceLabFHSWF/KG-Explorer>

Full Report: [TechnicalReportFusionWMApril2026.pdf](#) (37 pages)

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